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POSSIBILITIES OF ANTENATAL ULTRASOUND DIAGNOSIS OF CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS

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Annotation: In the course of the study, the possibilities of antenatal ultrasound diagnosis of some common heart malformations were studied. During the study, various congenital heart defects and their diagnosis using an ultrasound method were considered. Considering that congenital heart diseases are the most important cause of infant mortality due to congenital malformations, the diagnosis of fetal heart disease is the starting point for improving outcomes in critical congenital heart disease.

Keywords: pregnancy, congenital heart defects, ultrasound diagnostics

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ АНТЕНАТАЛЬНОЙ УЛЬТРАЗВУКОВОЙ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ВРОЖДЕННЫХ ПОРОКОВ СЕРДЦА

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Аннотация: В процессе исследования изучены возможности антенатальной ультразвуковой диагностики некоторых распространенных пороков развития сердца. В ходе исследования были рассмотрены различные врождённые пороки сердца и их диагностика с помощью УЗИ-метода. Учитывая, что ВПС являются самой важной причиной детской смертности из-за врожденных пороков, диагностика пороков сердца у плода является точкой отсчета для улучшения исхода при критических ВПС.

Ключевые слова: беременность, врожденные пороки сердца, ультразвуковая диагностика

Relevance. Fetal cardiology has changed significantly over the past 2 decades, largely in response to advances in imaging technologies and innovations in therapy. The diagnosis of fetal heart disease is most often made by ultrasound; however, new technologies are available, including 3D and 4D echocardiography, magnetic resonance imaging, fetal electrocardiography and magnetocardiography.

Among congenital malformations, the most common type of anomaly is congenital heart defect (CHD), which is associated with high perinatal, long-term morbidity and mortality. About 400 genes are involved in the development of congenital heart defects, including transcription factors, cellular signaling molecules and structural proteins important for heart development [1].

The frequency of CHD is approximately 8-10 per 1000 (0.8-1 %) full-term live births and may be 10 times higher in preterm infants (8.3 %). Moreover, this frequency is even higher in early pregnancy because some CHDs are complex and have been shown to cause fetal death. In fact, 50-60 % of congenital heart diseases require surgical correction, and 25 % of them are critical, and congenital heart disease is the leading cause of infant mortality. In such settings, survival, care, and developmental disabilities depend on the timing of diagnosis, delay in treatment, and severity of congenital heart disease. Therefore, it has been proven that early diagnosis of treatable congenital heart diseases reduces the risk of perinatal morbidity and mortality [2].

The database of the Belarusian Register of congenital malformations is replenished annually with more than 2.5 thousand

observations. The first place in the structure of registered developmental anomalies is occupied by heart defects, which in total account for about a third of all diagnosed cases (1 per 150 newborns).

The detection of congenital heart disease by fetal echocardiography for suspected cardiac anomaly on routine obstetric ultrasound is up to 40 % in low-risk populations. However, risk factors are identified only in 10 % of CHD cases. In this scenario, the heart should be examined in detail on a routine sonographic scan.

In the sonographic prenatal diagnosis of CHD, the fetal heart remains a challenging task involving sonographers, obstetricians, radiologists, and other fetal medicine specialists. High risk of developing heart defects and suspected cardiac anomaly on obstetric ultrasound, even in low-risk groups, are indications for referral for a detailed fetal echocardiogram.

Some defects, as a rule, not combined with life, can be detected in the first trimester of pregnancy – at the 13-14th week, but most of the defects can be diagnosed at the 18-22nd week of pregnancy (during the so-called second screening). Pregnant women at risk may be prescribed, in addition to planned, additional ultrasound [3].

The purpose of the work. Studying the possibility of antenatal ultrasound diagnosis of some common heart malformations.

Results and their discussion. Congenital malformations have a fairly extensive classification.

One of the most common congenital heart defects is a ventricular septal defect (VSD) (in the membranous or muscular part) or its absence at all. In the structure of congenital heart defects (CHDs), the ventricular septal defect is 20-32 % and occurs both in isolation and in combination with other heart defects. In an isolated form, it occurs in 25 % of all CHD cases, in combination with other defects – in 50 % of all CHD cases. Perimembranous defects account for 61-80 % of all cases of VSD, muscle defects – 5-20 %. The gender distribution is almost the same: girls (47-52 %), boys (48-53 %). Due to the high frequency of spontaneous closure of small ventricular septal defects, the frequency of this disease decreases with age, especially in adults. It is possible to diagnose VSD in an embryo during pregnancy already in the second or third trimester during screening ultrasound [4; 5].

Atrial septal defects (ASDs) account for approximately 6-10 % of congenital heart defects. Most cases are isolated and sporadic, but some are part of a genetic syndrome (eg, chromosome 5 mutations, Holt-Orham syndrome). The incidence of ASD ranges from 0.317 to 0,941 cases per 1000 live births, depending on the population, diagnostic methods and time of epidemiological studies.

The severity of circulatory disorders depends primarily on the size and location of the defect. Small sizes often do not lead to hemodynamic disturbances and do not require treatment, while large defects can lead to severe heart failure already in the neonatal period.

The diagnosis of atrial septal defect is suggested by cardiac examination, chest x-ray, ECG and confirmed by 2D color flow echocardiography and Doppler [6].

The exact incidence of patent ductus arteriosus (PDA) is unknown, as it is not clear from what moment to consider this defect as a pathology. It is conditionally believed that normally it should close during the first to two weeks of life. PDA usually occurs in preterm infants and is extremely rare in term infants. Under these criteria, the frequency of isolated pathology is about 0.14-0.30 per 1000 live births, 7 % among all HPUs and 3 % among critical HPUs. Diagnosis is suggested by clinical examination supported by chest x-ray and ECG and is established by 2D color flow echocardiography and Doppler [7].

Coarctation of the aorta is a congenital narrowing of the descending thoracic aorta that is usually (but not always) located immediately distal to the left subclavian artery, near the confluence of the patent ductus arteriosus. The incidence rate is 0.2-0.6 per 1000 newborns and, thus, aortic coarctation is 5-8 % of all cases of congenital heart defects. Coarctation is often associated with other congenital heart defects such as patent ductus arteriosus, bicuspid aortic valve, ventricular septal defect, and mitral valve anomalies.

Diagnosis is suggested by clinical examination (including blood pressure in all 4 limbs or femoral pulse), confirmed by chest x-ray and ECG, and established by 2D color flow echocardiography and Doppler imaging, and in older patients, with a suboptimal echocardiographic window using CT or MR angiography [8, 9].

Tetralogy of Fallot is formed as a result of abnormal development of the right heart of the fetus in the womb. The cause of this defect is

unknown. Tetralogy of Fallot has 4 signs: a large ventricular septal defect, obstruction of the vessels leaving the right ventricle and stenosis of the pulmonary valve, right ventricular hypertrophy and aortic dextroposition. Symptoms include cyanosis, dyspnea on feeding, slow growth, and severe dyspnea-cyanosis (sudden, potentially fatal episodes of severe cyanosis). Rough systolic murmurs are common in the upper left sternum, a single 2nd heart sound (S2) is typical. The final treatment is surgical correction of the defect. This is the most common cyanotic ("blue") heart disease, and is slightly more common in boys. Tetralogy of Fallot occurs in the amount of 4.7 per 10 thousand births. The diagnosis of tetralogy of Fallot is suggested on the basis of the history and clinical examination, supported by chest x-ray and ECG, and established by 2D color flow echocardiography and Doppler studies [10].

Conclusions. CHD is the most important cause of childhood death due to congenital malformations, so the diagnosis of fetal heart disease is the starting point for improving outcomes in critical congenital heart disease. Fetal heart screening remains a challenging task involving a team of professionals.

In the modern era, ultrasound has shown significant advances and it is expected that CHD will be diagnosed in detail during fetal life, which may improve the prognosis for most CHD cases. In addition, it is important to know the state of the cardiovascular system for a successful pregnancy outcome.

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